

Microwave assisted organic synthesis : A green chemical approach[†]

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There is a saying that "Preventing pollution and minimizing waste generation will gradually clean up our sins of the past". In this environmental conscious era, the role of chemistry and chemists¹ is to develop processes and design products, which can either eliminate or minimize the generation of toxic byproducts and other pollutants. Consequently, any new synthesis or chemical approach must include an element of environmental awareness. After almost one and half century of the first chemical revolution, a new kind of chemical revolution has come up i.e. "Green chemistry". The fundamental idea of green chemistry is that the manufacturer of any chemical needs to consider, what will be the fate of human life after this particular chemical is generated and used in society.

Twelve principles of green chemistry can be used to access a particular synthetic protocol's greenness². These principles address some basic aspects, such as use of various solvents; the amount of chemical waste produced; the use of catalyst and reagents (quantity and reusability); the amount of chemical step (energy efficiency) and atom economy; and the use of safer chemicals and reaction conditions. It is very difficult for a new synthetic protocol to satisfy all the 12 principles, which are not expected also, but if most of the principles are satisfied by a protocol, the developed process will be considered as a green route.

There are two alternative ways to categorize different approaches from green chemistry point of view.

(i) Synthesis via an environment friendly synthetic pathways or processes.

(ii) To develop some new benign replacements, which are capable of achieving the desired performance without any adverse human or ecological impacts.

This type of greener protocol can be achieved through a proper choice of starting materials (feed stock), atom economic methodologies with minimum chemical steps, the use of appropriate greener solvents and reagents, and efficient strategies for isolation of product and its purification. The green chemistry has emerged as a discipline that permeates all aspects of synthetic organic chemistry. Thus, a major goal of this endeavor should be to maximize simultaneously the efficient use of safer raw materials on one hand and to reduce the wastes produced in a particular process on the other.

Therefore, the need for green and sustainable synthetic methods in the fields of healthcare and fine chemicals like posing significant challenges to the synthetic organic chemists, the pressure to produce these substances expeditiously and that too in an environmentally benign fashion. These objectives can be easily achieved to a reasonable extent through the development of aqueous synthetic protocols using microwave radiations. It is worth-

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while to note that rapid development of "Green Organic Chemistry" is due to the recognition that ecofriendly products and processes will be economical in the long term as these do not require treatment of "end-of-the-pipe" pollutants, and byproducts so commonly generated by conventional synthetic procedures and one such technology is microwave assisted organic synthesis (MAOS)^{3,4}.

Microwave heating under controlled conditions is an invaluable technology because it not only dramatically reduces reaction times, typically from days or hours to minutes or even seconds, i.e. speed up the reaction, but it also fulfills the aim of green chemistry by reducing side reactions increasing yields and improving reproducibility⁵. This approach has now become a central tool in this rapid paced, time sensitive field and it has also blossomed into a useful technique for a variety of applications in organic synthesis, where high yielding protocols and facility of purification are highly desirable^{6,7}. Furthermore, this technique is energy efficient and the possibilities for application in combinatorial, parallel and automated environmentally benign chemistry are obvious. For all these reasons, the various possibilities offered by this technology are particularly suited to multistep synthesis and drug discovery processes with novel drug targets, where high yielding protocols and avoidance or facility of purification are highly desirable^{8,9}.

1.1. Microwaves as energy source

Microwave radiations are electromagnetic radiations, which are widely used as a source of heating in organic synthesis. Microwaves have enough momentum to activate reaction mixture to cross energy barrier and complete the reaction in lesser time. A microwave oven consists of a magnetron, a wave guide feed and an oven cavity. A magnetron is a thermionic diode that works on the principle of dielectric heating by converting part of the electric power into electromagnetic energy and the rest of it into heat energy. Microwaves occupy a place in the electromagnetic spectrum between infrared waves and radio waves, ranging in wavelengths between 0.01 and 1 m, and operate in a frequency range between 0.3 and 30 GHz. The typical bands for industrial applications are 915 ± 15 and 2450 ± 50 MHz. The wavelength between 1 cm and 25 cm are extensively used for RADAR transmissions and the remaining wavelength range is used for

telecommunications. The entire microwave region is therefore not available for heating applications and the equipment operating at 2.45 GHz, corresponding to a wavelength of 12.2 cm, is quite commonly used. The energy carried by microwave at 2.45 GHz is 1 joule per mole of quanta, which is relatively very small energy.

1.2. Microwaves as a tool for synthetic chemistry

Hull^{10,11} reported the earliest description of the magnetron (the high-power generator of microwave power), a diode with a cylindrical anode. The potential of microwave heating for organic synthesis has been explored in last two and half decades after the first reports appeared in 1986^{12,13}. Initially, reactions were performed in domestic microwave ovens using appropriate solvents. After that, several groups started investigating reactions in solvent free conditions including "dry media" usually with open vessels^{14,15}. Microwave induced organic reaction enhancement chemistry (MORE) has been described by Bose¹⁶⁻¹⁹ as a safe and convenient alternative to pressure reactions in unmodified microwave ovens. MW heating has not been restricted to organic chemistry only, but its application to various aspects of inorganic chemistry and polymer chemistry has also been investigated with several advantage of an ecofriendly approach.

In the past few decades, this technique has found a valuable place in the synthetic chemist's tool box, which is evident from a large number of publications²⁰⁻²⁶, particularly acetylation reaction²⁷, elimination reaction²⁸, alkylation reaction²⁹, alkynes metathesis³⁰, allylation reaction³¹, amination reaction³², aromatic nucleophilic substitution reaction³⁵, arylation reaction³⁴, carbonylation reaction³⁵, combinatorial reaction³⁶, condensation reaction³⁷, coupling reaction³⁸, cyanation reaction³⁹, cyclization reaction^{40,41}, cyclo-addition reaction⁴², deacetylation reaction⁴³, dehalogenation reaction⁴⁴, Diel's-Alder reaction⁴⁵, dimerization reaction⁴⁶, esterification reaction, transesterification reaction⁴⁷, enantioselective reaction⁴⁸, halogenation reaction⁴⁹, hydrolysis reaction⁵⁰, Mannich reaction⁵¹, oxidation reaction⁵², phosphorylation synthesis⁵³, polymerization reaction⁵⁴, rearrangement reaction⁵⁵, reduction reaction⁵⁶, ring closing synthesis⁵⁷, transformation reaction⁵⁸ etc. The initial slow development of this technology in the last 1980's and early 1990's has been attributed to lack of its controllability and reprodu-

cibility coupled with detail understanding of the basics of MW dielectric heating. The risk associated with the flammability of organic solvents in a MW field and the nonavailability of controlling systems for adequate temperature and pressure were the major concerns.

Principle

The basic principle behind the heating by microwaves is the interaction of charged particle of the reaction material with electromagnetic wavelength of a particular frequency. The phenomenon of producing heat by electromagnetic irradiation involves either collision or conduction and some time; both. Under microwave, two basic principles are involved to heat the materials, viz. dipole polarization and conduction mechanism.

(i) Dipolar polarization :

Dipolar polarization is the phenomenon responsible for the majority of microwave heating. It depends upon polarity of solvent and compound. In polar molecules, different electronegativities of individual atoms results in a permanent electric dipole, which is sensitive to external electric fields and will attempt to align with them by rotation. This realignment is rapid for a free molecule, but in liquid, the instantaneous alignment is prohibited by the presence of other molecules. A limit is, therefore, placed on the ability of the dipole to respond to an electric field, which affects the behaviour of the molecule with different frequencies of electric field e.g. under low frequency irradiation. The dipole may react by aligning itself in phase with the electric field. Molecules will polarize uniformly and thus, no random motion results. Some energy is gained in the molecule by this behaviour, and some is lost in collisions and the overall heating effect is small.

Under high frequency irradiation, the polar molecule will attempt to follow the field, but intermolecular inertia stops any significant motion before the field has reversed, in this case, the dipole do not have sufficient time to respond the field, and it does not rotate. As no motion is induced in the molecules, no energy transfers will take place, and therefore, no heating results. In case of intermediate frequency, the field will be such that the mole-

cule is almost (but not quite) able to keep in phase with the field polarity. The microwave frequency is low enough so that the dipoles have enough time to respond to the alternating field, and therefore to rotate, but high enough so that the rotation does not precisely follow the field. As the dipole reoriented to align itself with the field, the field is already changing, and a phase difference causes energy to be lost from the dipole in random collisions; thus, giving rise to dielectric heating (Fig. 1.1).

Fig. 1.1. Microwave heating by dipolar polarization mechanism.

(ii) Conduction mechanism :

The conduction mechanism generates heat through resistance to an electric current. The oscillating electromagnetic field generates an oscillation of electrons or ions in a conductor resulting in an electric current. This current faces internal resistance, which heats the conductor.

Fig. 1.2. Conduction mechanism.

When the irradiated sample is an electrical conductor, the charge carriers (electrons, ions etc.) are moved through the material under the influence of the electric field, resulting in a polarization. These induced currents will cause heating in the sample due to electrical resistance.

Microwave heating

For microwave heating to occur, there must be some

component of the reaction mixture that absorb the penetrating microwaves. Microwave radiation will penetrate the reaction mixture and if these are absorbed, then the energy will be converted into heat. The microwave couples directly with the molecules, leading to a rise in temperature. In typical reaction coordinate, the process begins with reactions, which have a certain potential energy level. In order to complete the transformation, this reaction must be activated to a transition state. Once reaching to this state, they quickly react and return to lower energy state (i.e. forms the product for the reaction). Microwave energy provides sufficient momentum to overcome the activation energy barrier and completes the reaction. In microwave heating, materials (reactants) can absorb the energy, can reflect the energy, or can simply pass the energy. There are few materials, which are either purely absorb, reflects or completely transparent to microwaves. Polar molecules are generally good absorbent to microwave radiation.

Microwave radiation will transfer energy in 10^{-9} s, with each cycle of the electromagnetic energy. Microwave heating affects the temperature parameters of rate equation. Most of such effects are due to high instantaneous heating of the substance above the normal bulk temperature. This is the primary factor in the observed rate enhancements. Microwave enhancement reaction can be faster by as much as 1000 fold. Microwave energy shifts the chemical reaction from kinetic control to thermodynamic control because of availability of high energy. With the elevated energy generated by the transfer of microwave energy, reactions which require many hours or even days to complete, have been completed in few minutes. Differential heating effects under microwave are due to the fact that the materials or components of a reaction mixture can differ in their ability to absorb microwave. Differential absorption of microwave will lead to differential heating and localized thermal inhomogeneities. In such cases, the component which absorbs microwave radiations, transfers heat to other components (which do not absorb) by conduction. Most of the catalysts absorb microwave radiation, which enhance various catalytic and enzymatic activities. Catalytic activation (e.g. palladium) is generally used in many synthetic reactions.

1.3. Microwave chemistry apparatus

Microwave synthesis has started with a kitchen mi-

crowave oven with good results. Now-a-days, many types of advanced microwave ovens have been introduced in the market. These consist of a microwave source (Magnetron), a microwave cavity or an applicator (multimode cavity or single mode cavity), mode stirrer, sensor probe (thermocouples or IR sensor) and software with digital display.

Two types of reactors are used for microwave assisted organic synthesis; these are multimode and mono mode reactors. The differentiating feature of a single mode apparatus is its ability to create a new standing wave pattern, which is generated by the interference of fields that have the same amplitude but different oscillating directions. This interface generates an array of nodes, where microwave intensity is zero and an array of antinodes, where the magnitude of microwave energy is at its highest. Therefore, sample should be placed at the antinode at appropriate distance from the magnetron.

Multimode reactors (domestic microwave ovens) are the most common instruments used in organic synthesis since they are comparatively inexpensive and readily available. Lot of satisfying organic synthesis has been done with domestic microwave ovens. Multimode reactors provide a field pattern with areas of high and low field strength, commonly referred to as "hot and cold spots" This non-uniformity of the field leads to the heating efficiency varying drastically between different positions of the sample. This drawback is overcome by the use of a mode stirrer.

The mode stirrer is a periodically moving metal vane that continuously changes the instantaneous field pattern in the cavity, and therefore, the field intensity is homogeneous everywhere throughout the cavity. Thus, samples can be placed anywhere inside the cavity, because the field is homogeneous throughout the cavity. In modern microwave reactors, preinstalled digital thermometers (sensors and probes) are used for temperature. Moreover, some sophisticated ovens are equipped with computers also^{59,60}.

1.4. Reaction vessels and reaction medium

The reaction vessel must be transparent to the microwaves. These are preferably be made up of teflon, polystyrene and glass^{61,62}. Metallic containers are not advisable as it gets heated soon due to preferential absorption

and reflection of rays. In microwave chemistry, the reaction medium plays an important role as reactions can be carried out in solvent or in solvent free conditions. For reactions in solvents, the solvent must have a dipole moment and a boiling point higher than the desired reaction temperature and a dielectric constant. Some of the solvents used commonly as microwave absorber are *N,N*-dimethylformamide or DMF (b.p. 154 °C, $\epsilon = 36.7$), formamide (b.p. 216 °C, $\epsilon = 111$), methanol (b.p. 65 °C, $\epsilon = 32.7$), ethanol (b.p. 78 °C, $\epsilon = 24.6$), chlorobenzene (b.p. 132 °C, $\epsilon = 5.6$), 1,2-dichlorobenzene (b.p. 180 °C), 1,2-dichloroethane (b.p. 83 °C), ethylene glycol (b.p. 196 °C, $\epsilon = 37.7$), dioxane (b.p. 101 °C), diglyme (b.p. 162 °C) and triglyme (b.p. 216 °C). The presence of salts in polar solvents can frequently enhance microwave coupling. Hydrocarbon solvents such as toluene ($\epsilon = 2.4$), hexane ($\epsilon = 1.9$), benzene ($\epsilon = 2.3$) and xylene, because of less dipole moment, are unsuitable as they absorb microwave radiation poorly. For solid state reactions, mineral oxides such as zeolite, alumina, silica montmorillonite K-10 clay etc. are used as absorbents.

1.5. Microwave effect^{63,64}

The phrase microwave effect applies to a range of observations in microwave chemistry. These may be classified in two categories : specific microwave and non-thermal microwave effects.

Specific microwave effects are those effects that cannot be easily emulated by conventional heating methods. Examples include : (i) selective heating of specific reaction components, (ii) rapid heating rates and temperature gradients, (iii) the elimination of wall effects and (iv) the superheating of solvents.

Non-thermal microwave effects are those effects, which explain unusual observations in microwave chemistry. As the name suggests, the effects do not require the transfer of microwave energy into thermal energy. Instead, the microwave energy itself directly couples to energy modes within the molecule or lattice. Non-thermal effects in liquids are almost certainly non-existent^{65,66}, as the time for energy redistribution between molecules in a liquid is much less than the period of a microwave oscillation. Non-thermal effects in solids are still debatable.

1.6. Heating under microwaves

Conventional heating usually involves the use of a furnace or oil bath, which heats the walls of the reactor by convection or conduction. The core of the sample takes much time to achieve the required temperature. However, microwave heating is able to heat the samples without heating the entire furnace or vessels, saving time and energy. However, due to the design of most microwave ovens and to uneven absorption by the object being heated, the microwave field is usually non-uniform and localized superheating occurs. Different compounds convert microwave radiation to heat by different amounts. This selectivity allows some parts of the object being heated more quickly or more slowly than others (particularly the reaction vessel).

When sample is irradiated with microwaves, there are certain zones within the sample, where temperature being much greater than the macroscopic temperature is called "hot spot". This is a thermal or heating effect that arises as a consequence of the inhomogeneity of the applied field. When polar solvents are submitted to microwave irradiation conditions, higher boiling point has been observed as compared with conventional heating. This has been attributed to some retardation of nucleation in microwave heating⁶⁷. This superheating has been related to the effect of stirring and the presence of a nucleating regulator. It is also related to the microwave power. This effect can be removed by adding boiling stones or stirring under low microwave power.

1.7. Comparison between microwave and conventional heating

Microwave radiation has proved to be highly effective heating source in chemical reactions. It provides rapid and homogeneous heating, which has certain advantages such as reaction rate acceleration, milder reaction conditions and higher chemical yields. In short, microwave enhanced chemical reactions are safer, faster, cleaner and more economical than conventional reactions. It helps in developing cleaner and greener synthetic routes⁶⁸⁻⁸².

1.7.1. Increased rate of reaction

Compared to conventional heating, microwave heating enhances the rate of certain chemical reactions by 10 to 1000 times. This is due to its ability to substantially

increase the temperature of a reaction. For instance, synthesis of fluorescein, which usually takes about 10 h by conventional heating methods, can be completed within 35 min only by means of microwave heating. Similarly, Biginelli's reaction is completed in 35 min under microwave irradiation whereas it requires 6 h by conventional method.

The rate acceleration caused by microwaves has been attributed to superheating of solvents (liquid phase reactions) and high temperature on the surface of catalyst or other solid reactants.

1.7.2. Efficient source of heating

Heating by means of microwave radiation is a highly efficient process and results in a significant energy saving. This is primarily because microwaves heat up just the sample and not the apparatus and therefore, energy consumption is less. A typical example is the use of microwave radiation in the ashing process.

1.7.3. Higher yields

In certain chemical reactions, microwave radiation produces higher yields as compared to conventional heating methods. For example, microwave synthesis of fluorescein results in an increase in the yield of the product from 70 to 82%. Similarly, yield of aspirin is 92% under microwave irradiation as compared to 85% by conventional method.

1.7.4. Uniform heating

Microwave radiation, unlike conventional heating methods, provides uniform heating throughout a reaction mixture. It is because in conventional heating, the walls of the oil bath gets heated first and then the solvent. As a result of this, there is always a temperature difference between the walls of the vessels and the solvent. On the other hand, in the case of microwave heating, only the solvent and the solute particles are excited, which results in uniform heating of the solvent. This feature allows the chemist to place reaction vessels at any location in the cavity of a microwave oven. It also proves vital in processing multiple reactions simultaneously, or in scaling up reactions that require identical heating conditions.

1.7.5. Selective heating

Selective heating is based on the principle that differ-

ent materials absorb microwaves to different extents. Some materials are transparent, where as others absorb microwaves. Therefore, microwaves can be used to heat a combination of such materials for example, the production of metal sulphide with conventional heating requires weeks because of the volatility of sulphur vapours while rapid heating of sulphur in a closed tube results in the generation of sulphur fumes, which can cause an explosion. However, in microwave heating, since sulphur is transparent to microwaves, only the metal gets heated. Therefore, reaction can be carried out at a much faster rate with rapid heating, without the threat of any explosion.

1.7.6. Environmental-friendly chemistry

Reactions conducted through microwaves are cleaner and more environment-friendly than conventional heating methods. Microwaves heat the compounds directly and therefore, use of solvents in the chemical reaction can be reduced or eliminated. An approach was developed to carry out a solvent free chemical reaction on solid support like clay, alumina, zeolite etc. The reactants, adsorbed on solid support under microwave, react at a faster rate than conventional heating. The use of microwaves has also reduced the extent of purification required for the end products of chemical reactions involving toxic reagents.

1.7.7. Greater reproducibility of chemical reactions

Reactions under microwave irradiation show more reproducibility as compared to conventional heating because of uniform heating and better control of process parameters. The temperature of chemical reactions can also be easily monitored. This is of particular relevance in the lead optimization phase of the drug development process in pharmaceutical companies.

1.8. Limitations of microwave chemistry

The limitations associated with microwave heating are its scalability, limited application and the hazards involved in its use.

1.8.1. Lack of scalability

The yield obtained by using domestic microwave apparatus is limited to a few grams. Although there have been developments in the recent past relating to the

scalability of microwave equipment, but still there is a gap that needs to be spelled to make this technology scalable.

1.8.2. Limited applicability

The microwaves can be used for heating only those materials, which absorb them. Microwaves cannot heat materials, which are transparent to these radiations.

1.8.3. Safety hazards

Although manufacturers of microwave heating apparatus have directed their research to make microwaves a safe source of heating, uncontrolled reaction conditions may result in undesirable results for example, chemical reactions involving volatile reactants under superheated conditions may result in explosive conditions. Moreover, improper use of microwave heating for rate enhancement of chemical reactions involving radioisotopes may result in uncontrolled radioactive decay.

1.8.4. Health hazards

Health hazards related to microwaves are caused by the penetration of microwaves. While microwaves operating at a low frequency range are only able to penetrate the human skin, higher frequency range microwaves can reach body organs. Research has proved that prolonged exposure to microwaves may result in the complete degeneration of body tissues and cells. It has also been established that constant exposure of DNA to high frequency microwaves during a biochemical reaction may result in complete degeneration of the DNA strand.

1.9. Classification of microwave reactions

Broadly microwave assisted organic synthesis can be classified into solvent assisted and solvent free synthesis.

1.9.1. Solvent assisted synthesis

Solvent assisted synthesis proceeds in the presence of solvent with good polarity, high boiling point and sufficient chemical stability. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF) is a good solvent for microwave assisted organic synthesis as it has a high boiling point (154 °C), high dielectric constant and is miscible with water, making it relatively easy to be removed from the reaction mixture. Erdelyi and Gogoll⁸³ showed the reaction of aryl halides with trimethylsilyl acetylene in DMF as solvent under micro-

wave radiations (eq. 1.1). They reported 85–95% yield of product in 5–25 min.

Bose *et al.*⁸⁴ synthesized protected amino acid from tetrachlorophthalic anhydride and glycine using DMF as solvent to yield 300 g of the product within 8 min. A dramatic increase in the overall speed of peptide synthesis was reported by Olivos *et al.*⁸⁵. Lin *et al.*⁸⁶ described the accelerated enzymatic digestion of several proteins in various solvent systems under microwave irradiation. Under the influence of rapid microwave heating, these enzymatic reactions can proceed in chloroform, which under traditional digestion conditions, renders the enzyme inactive. Hu *et al.*⁸⁷ carried out substitution of nitro group in presence of tetrahydrofuran in good yields (83%) (eq. 1.2).

Wang *et al.*⁸⁸ carried out reaction of aldehydes with pyrazolones in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate in aqueous medium. Cleavage of alkyl ethers in presence of pyridine and HCl was reported by Kulkarni *et al.*⁸⁹ (eq. 1.3).

Metha *et al.*^{90,91} synthesized and characterized some pyridine and quinazoline derivatives under microwave irradiation as potent antimicrobial agents while Parashar *et al.*⁹² made a comparison between conventional and

microwave assisted synthesis of some pyrazoline derivatives. A rapid and efficient methods for the preparation of isoxazole, pyrazole and pyrimidine derivatives of imidazolinone and quinazolinone under MWI has been reported by Vyas *et al.*⁹³. Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of some new annulated pyrimidinone derivatives has been done by Sancheti *et al.*⁹⁴.

1.9.2. Solvent-free synthesis

Solvent-free conditions offer safe and efficient reaction pathways, which are time saving, economic and often enable elimination of waste treatment. Solvent-free syntheses are subdivided into solid-support reaction and Neat reactions.

Solid-support reactions

Microwave assisted solid-support reactions profoundly increases the rate of reactions and decreases the reaction time. It also gives better conversion with high selectivity, avoiding solvent in most of cases and therefore, workup also becomes easier. In MW promoted deprotection, condensation, rapid one-pot synthesis, synthesis of heterocyclic compounds using recyclable mineral oxides supported reagents such as $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ -clay (clayfen), NH_2OH -clay, $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ -alumina, NaIO_2 -silica, CrO_3 -alumina, MnO_2 -silica and NaBH_2 -clay, zeolite etc. proved themselves as a base for the growth of a newer branch of green chemistry. Testero and Mata⁹⁵ reported synthesis of 3-(aryl)-alkenyl- β -lactams by an efficient application of olefin cross-metathesis on solid support. Kann⁹⁶ has studied use of polymer supported organometallic catalysts in organic synthesis. KF-alumina-mediated Bargellini reaction has been reported by Rohman and Myrboh⁹⁷.

Efficient and facile Ar-Si bond cleavage by Montmorillonite KSF has been given by Zafrani *et al.*⁹⁸ (eq. 1.5).

Bigi *et al.*⁹⁹ reported Montmorillonite KSF-catalysed regioselective trans-tert-butylation of tert-butylphenols. Lalitha and Sivakamasundari¹⁰⁰ studied the synthesis of few vinyl quinolones on solid support. Self-condensation of hydroxybenzene derivatives under microwave using heterogenous has been reported by Gomez *et al.*¹⁰¹ (eq. 1.6).

Marthala *et al.*¹⁰² demonstrated Beckmann rearrangement of ^{15}N -cyclohexanone oxime on zeolites silicate-1. Lalitha *et al.*¹⁰³ studied catalytic oxidative cleavage of C=N bond in the presence of zeolite H-NaX supported $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, as a green reagent. Rawal *et al.*¹⁰⁴ synthesized some Schiff bases on NaY zeolite. Kulkarni *et al.*¹⁰⁵ developed solvent-free synthesis of dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones over zeolite (eq. 1.7).

Mello *et al.*¹⁰⁶ reported silica-supported $\text{HgSO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ as a convenient reagent for the hydration of alkynes under mild conditions. Silica-supported LiHSO_4 has been developed as a highly efficient, heterogenous and reusable catalytic system for the solvent-free synthesis of β -enaminones and β -enaminoesters by Hasaninejad *et al.*¹⁰⁷ (eq. 1.8).

A solvent-free synthesis of 1,4-disubstitued-1,2,3-triazoles using neat azides and alkynes and a copper(I) polymer supported catalyst have been studied by Jialia *et al.*¹⁰⁸ (eq. 1.9).

Vyas *et al.*¹⁰⁹ reported microwave assisted synthesis and biological assay of 2-substituted [(morpholin-4-yl/4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-1*H*-benzimidazoles using acidic alumina as solid support.

Neat reactions

Such reactions are performed between neat reagents. Here, at least one of reagent must be a polar liquid. These are liquid-liquid or liquid-solid systems; the latter implies that the solid is soluble in the liquid phase or at least, the liquid counterpart is adsorbed on the solid and hence, the reaction occurs at the interface. Ameta *et al.*¹¹⁰ reported solvent-free synthesis of phthalimide derivatives under microwave irradiation. Microwave assisted one-pot synthesis of pyrazolone derivatives under solvent free conditions has been demonstrated by Ma *et al.*¹¹¹. Zhang *et al.*¹¹² developed a method for the solvent-free synthesis of pyrimidine nucleotide aminophosphate hybrids. A series of *NH*-pyrazoles were efficiently synthesized from the reaction of β -dimethylaminovinylketones and hydrazine hydrate in solid state by Longhi *et al.*¹¹³ (eq. 1. 10).

Ghorbani-Vaghei and Malaekhepour¹¹⁴ studied efficient and solvent-free synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols using *N,N,N',N'*-tetrabromobenzene-1,3-disulphonamide. Qu and Liu¹¹⁵ reported MW assisted solvent-free synthesis of 2',3',5',-tri-*O*-acetyl-2,6-dichloropurine nucleoside, catalyzed by *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (eq. 1.11).

LiBr has been used as a catalyst for solvent-free synthesis of fused thiazoloquinazoline derivatives¹¹⁶. Chang *et al.*¹¹⁷ carried out efficient solvent-free catalytic hydrogenation of solid alkenes and nitro-aromatics using Pd nanoparticles entrapped in aluminium oxy-hydroxide. $AlCl_3$ has been used as a catalyst for microwave enhanced and solvent-free green protocol for the production of dihydropyrimidine-2-(1*H*)-ones¹¹⁸ (eq. 1.12).

An efficient one-pot and solvent-free synthesis of chromenol[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives has been reported by Zonouzi *et al.*¹¹⁹ while microwave-assisted one-pot synthesis of octahydroquinazoline derivatives using ammonium metavanadate under solvent-free conditions was developed by Niralwad *et al.*¹²⁰. Strecker synthesis of α -amino nitriles from aldehydes and ketones under solvent-free conditions has been reported by Hajipour *et al.*¹²¹. A water-tolerant and reusable Lewis acid catalyst has been used for the one-pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1*H*)-ones under solvent-free conditions¹²². Solvent free synthesis of 4,6-diarylpyrimidin-2-(1*H*)-ones¹²³, 2,3-dihydrothiazoles¹²⁴, biquinolines¹²⁵, 14-substituted-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthenes¹²⁶, *N*-heteroarylaminonaphthols¹²⁷, phosphinidene anthrax[2,1-*b*]furan derivatives¹²⁸ have also been reported under neat conditions. Zinc chloride has been found to be an excellent catalyst for one-pot synthesis of nitriles under solvent free conditions¹²⁹. Li *et al.*¹³⁰ demonstrated efficient one-pot condensation of naphthol, aldehydes and cyclic 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds catalyzed by *p*-TSA under solvent-free conditions and sonication conditions.

1.10. Applications in organic synthesis

Green chemistry involves redesign and design of chemical synthesis to prevent pollution and thereby, solve the environmental problems. The microwave chemistry is the current approach in green chemistry, as it follows number of principles of green chemistry. Here, some applications of microwave assisted organic synthesis are reported.

1.10.1. Microwave assisted oxidation reactions

Lukasiewicz *et al.*¹³¹ carried out microwave assisted oxidation of some aromatics by hydrogen peroxide at supported tungsten catalyst. A remarkably fast microwave assisted selective oxidation of benzylic alcohols with calcium hypochlorite under solvent free conditions has been reported¹³². Alcohols are readily adsorbed on clayfen and rapidly oxidized to corresponding carbonyl compounds upon exposure to microwaves under solvent free conditions (eq. 1.13).

Under microwave irradiation, primary and secondary alcohols selectively oxidized to the corresponding aldehydes and ketones within 5–25 s using commercially available and magnetically retrievable magtrieve¹³³ (eq. 1.14).

The oxidations of some simple secondary alcohols by hydrogen peroxide-urea adduct (UHP) using microwaves has also been described¹³⁴. Tetravalent chromium dioxide, as a magnetically retrievable oxidant, has been shown to be a very useful oxidant for microwave assisted and conventional transformation of aromatic and alkyl aromatic molecules into the corresponding aryl ketones, quinones or lactones¹³⁵. An acceleration has been reported under MWI in metal-catalyzed oxidation reactions of the amino acids bound to Cu in metalloprotein¹³⁶. Bogda and Lukasiewicz¹³⁷ carried out MW assisted oxidation of alcohols using aqueous hydrogen peroxide and commercially available catalysts. Microwave assisted synthesis of lactones and solvatochromic 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines in the presence of barium manganate has been reported by Bagley *et al.*^{138,139}. Liu *et al.*¹⁴⁰ studied size effect of silica-supported gold clusters in the microwave assisted oxidation of benzyl alcohol with H₂O₂. Oxidation of benzylic alcohols using Koser's reagent under solvent free conditions using MW irradiation has been described by Lee *et al.*¹⁴¹.

1.10.2. Microwave assisted reduction reaction

Bose *et al.*^{142,143} were first to report the use of microwaves for hydrogenation in organic synthesis. A series of β -lactam derivatives were hydrogenated using formates and Pd/C or Raney Ni as catalyst. Schmogger *et al.*¹⁴⁴ carried out microwave assisted reduction of organic compounds using catalytic and stoichiometric reactions. Ethylene glycol was used as the solvent and electron source for the microwave-assisted reduction reaction. An improved microwave-assisted one-pot tandem Staudinger/aza-Wittig/reduction was reported by Chen *et al.*¹⁴⁵ for the synthesis and biological activity of novel 5'-arylamino-nucleosides. Yanagida *et al.*^{146,147} carried out the reductive dehalogenation of chlorinated phenols to phenol, cyclohexanol and other chlorine-free compounds within 20 min using MWI. Microwave-assisted reduction of carbonyl compounds in solid state using sodium borohydride supported on alumina has been studied by Varma and Saini¹⁴⁸ (eq. 1.15).

Fagury-Neto and Kiminami¹⁴⁹ discovered the synthesis of Al₂O₃/Mullite/SiC powders by microwave assisted carbothermal reduction of Kaolin.

1.10.3. Microwave assisted alkylation

MW assisted selective *N*-alkylation of 6-amino-2-thiouracil in DMF using different alkyl halides has been investigated by Loupy *et al.*¹⁵⁰ (eq. 1.16) whereas no reaction was observed under the same conditions in a thermoregulated oil bath. Syntheses of *N*-alkyl phthalimides and *N*-alkyl succinimides have been reported on silica gel in dry media under MW and PTC conditions¹⁵¹.

A series of diethers have been obtained by alkylation of dianhydrohexanes under MW conditions¹⁵² at 140 °C in 90% yield. Matondo and coworkers¹⁵³ carried out *O*-alkylation of *o*-bromophenol under MW conditions using TBAB as catalyst (eq. 1.17) Reddy *et al.*¹⁵⁴ reported the alkylation of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin with desyl chloride under MW conditions to synthesize desyl ethers Lindau *et al.*^{155,156} reported MW assisted exposure *o*-methylation of carboxylic acids using polymer supported *o*-methylisourea.

(eq. 1.17)

Askira *et al.*¹⁵⁷ carried out *S*-alkylation by reacting 6-mercaptobenzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline with dibromo derivatives under MW assisted PTC conditions.

1.10.4. Microwave assisted rearrangements

Loupy and Regnier¹⁵⁸ compared Beckmann rearrangement of benzaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenones oximes by conventional and MW heating. They found that yields are significantly enhanced under microwave exposure (eq. 1.18).

(eq. 1.18)

Microwave-assisted double decarboxylative Claisen rearrangement has been reported by Craig *et al.*¹⁵⁹ while Li *et al.*¹⁶⁰ carried out Beckmann rearrangement in acetone under microwave irradiation using silica sulfate as an efficient and recyclable catalyst (eq. 1.19).

(eq. 1.19)

Deepak *et al.*¹⁶¹ reported an efficient methodology for selective Claisen rearrangement of allyl aryl ethers

using H β zeolite as mild, inexpensive and green catalyst under microwave irradiation in the absence of solvent (eq. 1.20).

(eq. 1.20)

The Wolf rearrangement of α -diazoketones under microwave irradiation to β -amino acids with retention of configuration in good yield (91–95%) has been described by Patil *et al.*¹⁶². An aza-Cope rearrangement of *N*-allylanilines within few minutes, using BF₃·OEt₂ under microwave activation has been studied by Gonzalez *et al.*¹⁶³ Microwave assisted Hoffmann rearrangement has been reported by Miranda *et al.*¹⁶⁴ (eq. 1.21)

(eq. 1.21)

1.10.5. Microwave assisted cycloaddition

Microwave assisted Diels-Alder cycloaddition reaction between of 2-fluoro-3-methoxy-1,3-butadiene and ethylene was studied by Patrick *et al.*¹⁶⁵ (eq. 1.22)

(eq. 1.22)

This reaction gives moderate yield under thermal conditions, but results in a very good yield under microwave radiation. Similarly, intramolecular hetero Diels-Alder cycloaddition of acetylenic pyrimidines to give bicyclic pyridine was reported by Shao¹⁶⁶. Microwave assisted synthesis of a [3 + 2] cycloaddition library was studied by Wilson *et al.*¹⁶⁷. The products were purified by solid supported reagent. Similarly, hetero [6 + 3] cycloaddition of fulvenes with *N*-alkylidene glycine esters was observed by Hong *et al.*¹⁶⁸. Synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines by cycloaddition reactions under microwave irradiation was carried out by Diaz *et al.*¹⁶⁹. Synthesis of pyridylpyrrole from *N*-acylated amino acids via 1,3-di-

polar cycloaddition was found to be accelerated, when performed under microwave irradiation¹⁷⁰. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition of alkynes and azides yielding triazoles requires harsh conditions, i.e. high temperature and longer reaction times. However, Taherpour and Faraji¹⁷¹ reported Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of sodium azide and 9-bromophenanthrene to give 1*H*-phenanthro[9,10-*d*][1,2,3]triazole in good yields under MWI. The reaction was completed only 45 s (eq. 1.23).

(eq. 1.23)

1.10.6. Microwave assisted condensation

Zaydi and Borik¹⁷² carried out microwave assisted condensation reactions of 2-aryl hydrazonopropanals with dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate under solvent free conditions. Microwave assisted Knoevengel condensation under solvent free conditions has been studied by Mallouk *et al.*¹⁷³ using hydroxyapatite as a catalyst and reported yield is also high. Ighilahriz *et al.*¹⁷⁴ synthesized 4(3*H*)-quinazolinones by cyclocondensation of anthranilic acid, aniline and orthoester (or formic acid) in presence of HPA as a catalyst under MWI (eq. 1.24).

(eq. 1.24)

Agrawal and Joshipura¹⁷⁵ studied Friedlander condensation under microwave irradiation. They also made a comparison with conventional method. In Friedlander condensation, a mixture of 2-aminobenzophenone and ethyl acetoacetate was irradiated for 5–7 min without catalyst and the products were obtained in good yields (80–91%).

Microwave assisted aldol condensation has been reported by Gupta *et al.*¹⁷⁶ and Elder *et al.*¹⁷⁷. Microwave assisted synthesis of hydroxycyclopentenones via cross aldol condensation of benzil with various ketones was reported by Marjani *et al.*¹⁷⁸.

1.10.7. Microwave assisted protection reaction

Microwave in addition to its massive applications in rapid organic synthesis, may also be used for simple protection reactions. Microwave assisted selective protection of glutaraldehyde and its monoacetals and thioacetals were carried out by Flink *et al.*¹⁷⁹. They reported that reactions proceed efficiently and only traces of deprotected materials were left (eq. 1.25).

(eq. 1.25)

Similarly, microwave assisted hydrolysis of *N*-methoxy-*N*-methyl amide, which act as a protecting group for carboxylic acid for the synthesis of (*R*)-5-hydroxyalkanoic acid was reported by Jaipuri *et al.*¹⁸⁰. They synthesized (*R*)-3-hydroxydecanoic acid (eq. 1.26).

(eq. 1.26)

Liu *et al.*¹⁸¹ carried out graft polymerization of ϵ -caprolactone on chitosan under microwave irradiation via a protection-graft deprotection procedure with phthaloylchitosan in presence of stannous octoate as a catalyst. After deprotection, the phthaloyl group was removed and amino group was regenerated. A rapid microwave assisted deprotection of *N*-benzyl carbamate and other *N*-benzyl derivatives in solution was also reported¹⁸². In this report, amino group was protected as benzyl carbamates and this benzyl group is then easily deprotected by microwave assisted transfer hydrogenation with palladium charcoal in isopropanol and ammonium formate in MeO-PEG as solid support.

Rajabi and Saidi¹⁸³ described efficient and simple protection method for aldehydes using trimethyl orthoformate and methanol under microwave irradiation. This reaction is chemoselective. Only aldehydes are converted into acetals while ketones do not react.

1.10.8. Microwave assisted transition metal catalyzed coupling reactions

Organometallic catalysis in general and palladium catalyzed reactions in particular have emerged as the success stories in the growing heterogeneous field of microwave assisted chemistry^{184,185}. The first MW-promoted Suzuki coupling was published in 1996¹⁸⁶. Microwave accelerated metal-catalyzed transformation of aryl and vinyl halides by carboxylations, Heck and Sonogashira reactions and cross coupling have been reported by Nilsson *et al.*¹⁸⁷(eq. 1.27).

Stadler and Kappe¹⁸⁸ observed rapid formation of triarylphosphines by microwave assisted transition metal catalyzed cross-coupling reactions. Microwave flash heating accelerate transition metal catalyzed homogeneous reactions including Heck coupling, cross-coupling and asymmetric substitution¹⁸⁹. Walla and Kappe¹⁹⁰ carried out microwave assisted Negishi and Kumada cross coupling reactions of aryl chlorides. Perbenzylated pyranoid glycols couples with aryl bromides under MWI in the presence of 5% mol palladium(II) acetate in DMF to produce 2',3'-unsaturated *C*-aryl-*D*-glycopyranosides in a rapid and stereospecific manner¹⁹¹.

Synthesis of differently substituted 2(1*H*)-pyrazinones under microwave assisted palladium catalyzed phosphonium coupling reaction has been reported¹⁹². Zhao *et al.*¹⁹³ described Pd catalyzed cross-coupling reactions

of diazirines with aryl halides under microwave heating conditions to give a series of substituted olefins in 32–96% yields (eq. 1.28).

Leadbeater^{194,195} reported Suzuki-Miyaura coupling in aqueous medium and isolated products in good yields. Fluoride free cross-coupling reactions under ligand free conditions with low Pd loadings in water using NaOH under microwave heating has been carried out by Najera and Alacid¹⁹⁶.

1.10.9. Microwave assisted synthesis of heterocycles

The efficient use of MW heating approach in several organic synthesis as an emerging green technique has been proposed by several workers^{197,198}. Zhao *et al.*¹⁹⁹ discovered a general microwave-assisted protocol for the expedient synthesis of quinoxalines and heterocyclic pyrazines. The synthesis of pyrroles by reaction of hexane-2,5-dione with primary amines has been carried out by Danks²⁰⁰ under microwave irradiation (eq. 1.29).

Larhed and Halberg²⁰¹ synthesized functionalized quinoxalines and heterocyclic pyrazines in excellent yields from 1,2-diketone intermediates under microwave irradiation. Kruithof *et al.*²⁰² reported microwave assisted multicomponent synthesis of some heterocycles. Youssef and Amin²⁰³ carried out microwave assisted synthesis of some new heterocyclic spiro-derivatives with potential antimicrobial and antioxidant activity. MW assisted synthesis of benzimidazoles (as potential HIV-1 integrase inhibitors) by condensation of *R*-hydroxycinnamic acids with 1,2-phenylenediamine in water was performed by Ferro *et al.*²⁰⁴. A simple, high yielding synthesis of 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazoles from 1,2-diketones and aldehydes in the presence of ammonium acetate was reported by Wolkenberg *et al.*²⁰⁵ under MWI.

Microwave assisted one pot tandem reaction for direct conversion of primary alcohols and aldehydes to triazines and tetrazoles in aqueous medium was described by Shie and Fang²⁰⁶. Gududura *et al.*²⁰⁷ reported one pot protocol for the preparation of 4-thiazolidinones using microwave irradiation in the presence of *N,N*-diisopropyl ethylamine (DIEA) base in ethanol (eq. 1.30).

A variety of functionalized flavones and chromones in very high yields by the cyclization of 1-(2-hydroxyaryl)-1,3-propanediones has been described²⁰⁸. Regio-specific one-pot synthetic procedure of pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives under MWI has been reported by Prajapati *et al.*²⁰⁹. The Hantzsch related one-pot synthesis of *N*-substituted actinide derivatives under open vessel reflux conditions in a domestic microwave oven was reported by Hu *et al.*²¹⁰. Highly functionalized sugar-heterocyclic hybrid through one-pot synthesis of novel sugar derived 5,6-dihydro-quinazolino[4,3-*b*]quinazolin-8-ones has been proposed by Roy *et al.*²¹¹. Desai *et al.*²¹² prepared a library of 144 member of furocoumarin via three component reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarins, isocyanides and aldehydes.

1.10.10. Microwave assisted synthesis of nanocomposites

Wang and Lee²¹³ carried out microwave-assisted synthesis of SnO₂-graphite nanocomposite for Li-ion battery applications. Polyacrylamide-metal nanocomposites with metal nanoparticles homogeneously dispersed in the polymer matrix have been successfully prepared using corresponding metal salt and acrylamide monomer in ethylene glycol by microwave heating²¹⁴. Microwave-assisted synthesis of Zn-Al-layered double hydroxide-sodium dodecyl sulfate nanocomposite has been reported by Hussein *et al.*²¹⁵. Rapid synthesis of Pt or Pd/carbon nanocomposites using microwave irradiation has also been carried out^{216,217}. Mallikarjuna and Varma²¹⁸ described shape controlled bulk synthesis of noble nanocrystals and their catalytic properties under microwave irradiation. Development of Mg/Cu nanocomposite using microwave assisted rapid sintering has also been reported by Wong

and Gupta²¹⁹. Pt-Ru/carbon fiber nanocomposites have been prepared using a bimetallic precursor as source of metal under microwave irradiation²²⁰. UV curable organic/inorganic hybrid nanocomposites with high refractive indices, moderate hardness, good adhesive strength and excellent gas blocking performances have been synthesized rapidly *in situ* microwave heating process²²¹. Chen and Wang²²² reported microwave-assisted synthesis of a Co₃O₄⁻ graphene sheet-on-sheet nanocomposite as a superior anode material for Li-ion batteries. In addition, number of publication related to microwave assisted synthesis of nanocomposites have appeared in recent past years²²³⁻²²⁹.

1.10.11. Microwave assisted synthesis of ionic liquids

A microwave assisted preparation of a series of ambient temperature ionic liquids, 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium halides via efficient reaction of 1-methylimidazole with alkyl halide under solvent-free conditions has been reported by Varma and Namboodiri²³⁰. Khadilkar and Rebeiro²³¹ reported the synthesis of various alkyl pyridinium and 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium halide under microwave exposure in a closed vessel (eq. 1.31).

Law *et al.*²³² reported solvent-free route to ionic liquid precursors using a water-moderated microwave process (eq. 1.32).

Several Bronsted acid ionic liquids have been synthesized and used as solvents and catalysts for three-component Mannich reactions of aldehydes and amines at 25 °C²³³. Wassercheid²³⁴ reported continuous reactions using ionic liquids as catalytic phase. Unique role of ionic liquid in microwave assisted synthesis of monodispersed

magnetic nanoparticles has been studied by Hu *et al.*²³⁵. Rahman *et al.*²³⁶ carried out microwave-assisted Bronsted acidic ionic liquid-protonated one-pot synthesis of heterobicyclic dihydropyrimidinones by a three-component coupling of cyclopentanone, aldehydes and urea. Microwave-assisted fast synthesis of optically active polyamides in ionic liquid containing methionine linkages has been reported by Mallakpour and Seyedjamali²³⁷. Catalytic oxidation reactions in ionic liquids using H₂O₂ as oxidant in presence of transition metal catalysts and metal-free catalysts were reviewed by Gharnati *et al.*²³⁸ Chen *et al.*²³⁹ reported microwave assisted Diels-Alder reactions in water and in ionic liquids.

1.10.11. Miscellaneous

In addition to above, microwave heating processes have been employed for regio-selective and chemo-selective synthesis, polymer synthesis, ceramic products, intercalation products, organometallic and coordination compounds, macromolecules, radiopharmaceuticals etc. Mallakpour and Rafiemanzelat²⁴⁰ reported microwave assisted polycondensation of optically active poly (amide-imide). Faghihi *et al.*²⁴¹ investigated a facile synthesis of novel optically active poly (amide-imide)s containing *N,N'*-(pyromellitoyl)-bis-1-phenylalanine diacid chloride and 5,5-disubstituted hydantoin derivatives under microwave irradiation. Zhao *et al.*²⁴² reported the synthesis of bis-intercalaters with an aminochloropyrimidine ring as potential anticancer agents.

Various molecules like carboranes²⁴³, quinazolinones²⁴⁴, phenol-formaldehyde resole²⁴⁶, phenothiazine²⁴⁷, 4,5-disubstituted pyrazolopyrimidines²⁴⁸ and curcumin analogs²⁴⁹ have been synthesized by microwave heating method with high efficiency. Synthesis of a variety of transition metal coordination compounds²⁵⁰ under atmospheric conditions has been carried out under MW radiations. A particularly useful application of microwave assisted synthesis at elevated pressure has been the preparation of radiopharmaceuticals containing isotopes with short half lives such as C-11 and F-18²⁵¹⁻²⁵³. In addition, microwave assisted synthesis of macromolecules like epoxyresins²⁵⁴⁻²⁵⁶, polyesters²⁵⁷, polyethers^{258,259}, poly (aspartic acid)^{260,261} and polyphosphazene²⁶² have been reported. Hao *et al.*²⁶³ used microwave irradiation for the stereoselective synthesis of aminoketenes.

Microwave assisted chemical synthesis has advantages like reaction acceleration, yield improvement, enhanced physicochemical properties and the evolvement of new material phases. Shi and Hwang²⁶⁴ demonstrated the significance of these advantages to industrial applications. Looking to the importance of MWI in synthetic chemistry, it can be concluded that the time is not far off, when microwave heating technique will almost replace the conventional techniques, not only in laboratory but in industries also. They will truly become the Bunsen burner of the 21st century. But still there are rooms to investigate this field and to develop greener routes to synthesize other useful compounds for the benefit of mankind.

Ultimately, we can conclude that microwave mediated synthesis is a green chemical technology because microwave not only accelerate chemical processes but also improve yield, selectivity, reduces pollution and enable reactions to occur in solvent free conditions.

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